

Clean and rapid biomimetic synthesis of gold nanoparticles using all parts of the aquatic weed water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*)[†]

Tasneem Abbasi^a, J. Anuradha and S. A. Abbasi*

Centre for Pollution Control and Environmental Engineering, Pondicherry University,
Puducherry-605 014, India

E-mail : abbasi.cpee@gmail.com

^aConcurrently with Department of Fire Protection Engineering, Worcester Polytechnic Institute,
Worcester, MA 01609, USA

Abstract : A bioinspired method of gold nanoparticles synthesis utilizing the highly invasive aquatic weed, *Eichhornia crassipes*, is presented. In an attempt to utilize the entire plant, the extracts of all its parts – leaves, petiole and root – were employed in various proportions with the gold precursor, HAuCl₄ solution, for the synthesis. The reduction of gold ions to nanoparticles was tracked using UV-Vis spectroscopy. The electron micrographs of the synthesized nanoparticles revealed the presence of particles of monodispersed spherical and polydispersed pentagonal, hexagonal, rod, truncated triangle and spherical shapes in sizes ranging 4–30 nm and 57–96 nm respectively. The presence of gold atoms was confirmed from the EDAX and X-ray diffraction studies. The FT-IR spectral study indicated that the proteins and polyols in the plant extract could have been responsible for the reduction of the gold ions to gold nanoparticles.

Keywords : Gold nanoparticles, biomimetic, water hyacinth, anisotropy.

Introduction

Nanoparticles can be synthesized by physical, chemical and biological means but the first two routes often entail the use of high energy inputs and/or high temperatures and pressures. Toxic chemicals are also often employed. In contrast biological methods which use microorganisms, algae, or plant extracts to generate nanoparticles in a way it is done in nature i.e. by biomimetics – are much cleaner and ‘greener’. This aspect has bestowed great relevance to the field of biomimetic nanoparticles synthesis. Of these the plant-based synthesis is found to be quicker and simpler than microorganism-based synthesis^{1,2}. It also doesn't carry the risk of microbial contamination which can be an issue if the nanoparticles are used in food-making or in medicine^{3,4}.

The use of plant extracts to extra-cellularly synthesize metallic nanoparticles is a recently developed approach. Beginning with the pioneering work of Shanker *et al.*⁵, several authors have successfully used extracts of different plants – mainly the leaves for extracellular synthesis of nanoparticles. The work has been reviewed on several occasions^{6,2,7-9} and is characterized by two attributes :

(i) in a vast majority of reports plants which have well-established uses such as for food, medicines, cosmetics, and ornamental have been employed and (ii) only one or the other part of the plants, mostly leaves, have been employed.

The first attribute brings it into conflict with well-established uses of the concerned plants as also makes the nanoparticle manufacture costlier due to the alternative marketability of the plants involved in it. The second attribute reduces the extent of utilizability of the plants further. The present work has aimed to harness all the advantages associated with plant-based biomimetic nanoparticle synthesis while steering it away from plant species which have other, well-recognized and well-established, uses. To achieve this dual objective we have explored the use of aqueous leaf, petiole and root extracts of a very problematic invasive weed *Eichhornia crassipes* for the synthesis of gold nanoparticles (GNPs). The distinguishing features of the present work is that it (a) enables the synthesis GNPs by a facile, non-hazardous, energy-saving, and cost effective method; (b) it simultaneously enables gainful utilization of an obnoxious

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

invasive weed which, in addition to being worthless, is also harmful to the environment, and for which enormous costs are incurred with risks to the environment from herbicide use just to keep it in check².

A few attempts have been made in the past to use water hyacinth in the synthesis of silver nanoparticles^{10,11} but there is no report on the possible use of the weed in the manufacture of GNPs. On the other hand, it is important to develop methods for GNP synthesis owing to the GNP's special attributes, due to which GNPs find wide applications as bioelectrochemical sensors, in diagnostics and detection, and for drug delivery. GNPs are able to almost fully retain their bioactivities even when allowing stable immobilization of their biomolecules¹². This proves highly advantageous in the making of sensitive biosensors. GNPs permit direct electron transfer between redox protein and bulk electrode materials in electroensing devices thereby obviating the need to have an electron transfer mediator¹³. GNPs are also among the most intensively studied of noble metal nanoparticles due to their ability in efficiently catalyzing the conversion of solar energy into chemical energy¹⁴. This ability stems from the fact that the optical absorption of GNP cover almost the full solar spectrum¹⁵ and they can catalyze chemical reactions under UV as well as visible light irradiation. GNP have also been applied in numerous other ways in chemical, biochemical, pharmaceutical, and electronic industry. Hence we have explored the use of water hyacinth in GNPs synthesis and have identified factors which can help in controlling the shapes and sizes of the manufactured GNPs.

E. crassipes is a free-floating aquatic macrophyte belonging to the Pontederiaceae family and is widely regarded as the world's most widespread of aquatic weeds. It is present throughout the tropics and sub-tropics. In India, water hyacinth infestation was reported for the first time in Bengal at the beginning of 1890. By now the weed is almost ubiquitous in India, present everywhere except in the severely arid parts of Rajasthan and the Kashmir valley.

The rampant growth of the plant causes the following problems : impairs commercial navigation; degrades and deteriorates water quality; disrupts hydropower generation; increases flood frequency, duration and intensity; reduces species diversity; increases extinction rate of rare, threatened and endangered species; provides habitat for

insect-borne disease vectors; alters animal community interactions; causes recreational navigation impairment; interferes with safe swimming; changes sediment chemistry; interferes with fishing; reduces water storage capacity in reservoirs, tanks, ponds; impedes flow of water in canals and drainage systems; and reduces fish production. In addition the weed exerts allelopathic effect.

Attempts to utilize water hyacinth have spanned a gamut : for wastewater treatment, as a fertilizer, for paper making, for making furniture and handicraft, as an adsorbent for the removal of organics and heavy metals, as an algacide, as an animal feed, as a source of protein, as compost for mushroom culture, for ethanol production, for hydrogen production, for biogas generation and as a substrate for vermicomposting. However, none of the potential uses have been economically viable at a scale large enough for it to be used as a means to manage and reduce the spread of the weed. Moreover, none of the methods utilize all the parts of the plant; thus leaving one or the other parts unused.

Experimental

Preparation of aqueous extracts of the leaf, petiole and root of water hyacinth :

E. crassipes was collected from its natural habitat near Pondicherry (Central) University, Puducherry. The fresh, mature, and disease-free plant parts were washed thoroughly with water, then dipped in saline water to sterilize their surface, followed by washing them liberally before blotting them dry. A known quantity of plant samples was dried at 105 °C to a constant weight¹⁶. On the basis of dry weight thus obtained, extracts for nanoparticle synthesis were made by boiling 1.0 g dry weight equivalent of the plant material with 100 ml of sterile distilled water for 5 min. The contents were filtered through a Whatmann no. 42 filter paper and the filtrate was stored under refrigeration at 4 °C^{7,17,9,18}. Reconnoitery experiments indicated that the extracts retained their integrity for upto 3 days, as evidenced by the extent of intensity of nanoparticles generated by them. Hence in all the experiments the extracts were used within 3 days of preparation.

Au^{III} solution :

A 10⁻³ M aqueous solution of Au^{III} was prepared using analytical reagent grade HAuCl₄. The stock solution was stored in amber bottles covered with black sheets.

Nanoparticle synthesis :

The plant extracts were mixed with Au^{III} solution at ambient temperature. The gold nanoparticles (GNPs) began forming almost immediately as indicated by the appearance of pinkish red or purple colour which grew in intensity with time. The developed colour and its intensity depended on the stoichiometric ratio in which the plant extract and the metal ion had been mixed.

Characterization of the synthesized gold nanoparticles :

UV-Visible spectroscopy :

UV-Visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy is an essential means to track the synthesis of the aqueous metal nanoparticles. The bioreduction of the gold ions was monitored by recording the UV-Vis spectra in the range of 190–1100 nm for the reaction mixture filled in quartz cuvettes with 1 cm path length at our laboratory. De-ionized distilled water was used as blank. The spectral observation of the reaction mixtures were recorded by employing Labindia (Model UV 3000⁺) and ELICO (Model SL 164) double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometers operated at 1 nm resolution.

SEM/TEM studies :

SEM (Scanning electron microscopy) and TEM (Transmission electron microscopy) studies were carried out to determine the size and morphology of the synthesized gold nanoparticles. The synthesized gold nanoparticles present in the extract and unreduced metal ion solution mixture were centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 20 min using Remi C 24 centrifuge. The resulting pellets were washed thrice with de-ionized distilled water to remove the unreacted constituents and were re-dispersed in de-ionized distilled water.

The samples for SEM studies were prepared by placing a drop of suspension on a carbon-coated SEM grid. The micrographs were recorded by employing a scanning electron microscope (SEM). For high resolution scanning electron microscopic studies the samples were prepared by placing dried pellets on a carbon coated aluminium stub. The nanoparticles were prepared for TEM studies by first pelletizing the nanoparticles by diluting and through sonication. The micrographs were recorded by depositing a drop of the well dispersed samples on carbon coated 300 mesh placed on copper TEM grids and excess liquid was wiped off with filter paper.

Energy dispersive X-ray (EDAX) studies :

The identification of the elemental composition of the synthesized nanoparticles was performed using the EDAX equipment attached with the SEM/HRSEM microscopes. The EDX spectrum was recorded after documenting the electron micrographs in the spot-profile mode by focusing on the densely occupied gold nanoparticle region.

Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) studies :

The SAED pattern recorder was equipped with TEM instrument; hence the SAED patterns were documented along with the TEM micrographs.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) studies :

The powder XRD (X-Ray Diffraction) spectrum of the NPs was recorded to investigate the crystallinity of the material being analyzed. An aliquot of the pelletized gold nanoparticles was drop-casted to thin film on a glass slide and the spectral recording was executed by scanning in the 2 θ region, from 0° to 80°, at 0.02° per minute and with the time constant of 2 s. The crystalline pattern of the nanoparticles was recorded using Cu K $_{\alpha 1}$ radiation with a wavelength (λ) of 1.5406 Å at a tube voltage of 40 kV and a tube current of 30 mA.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopic (FTIR) studies :

FT-IR spectroscopy was used to help identify the functional groups involved in the reduction, stabilization and capping of the gold nanoparticles. For performing the FT-IR studies, the samples were dried completely and ground with potassium bromide. The spectrum was recorded at diffuse reflectance mode with 4 cm⁻¹ resolution in the mid-IR region between the wavenumbers 4000 and 400 cm⁻¹.

Results and discussion

UV-Visible spectra :

The onset of gold nanoparticles formation was seen from the gradual appearance of pinkish red/violet color within 10 min of mixing the metallic solution with the plant extract. The colour change is attributed to the localized surface plasmon resonance (SPR), which is the collective oscillation of free conduction electrons induced by an interacting electromagnetic field of the nanoparticles¹⁹.

Depending on the plant part used for preparing the extract and its proportions with respect to the metal solu-

tion, two types of spectra were observed – type I with a single λ_{max} in the visible region, and type II with two λ_{max} 's; one in the visible region and the other in the NIR (near infra-red) region. The reaction combinations LE₁, PE₁ and RE₁ (Figs. 1a, 2a and 2c) exhibited the former type of spectra while the LE₂, PE₂ and RE₂ (Figs. 1b, 2b and 2d) combinations exhibited the latter. The presence of a sharp SPR peak in the visible region in the spectra of LE₁, PE₁ and RE₁ reaction combinations indicated that it might have occurred due to the transverse (out-of-plane) plasmon resonance (TPR), which is exhibited by spherical nanoparticles. This was confirmed from the SEM and TEM studies, which showed that the synthesized particles were indeed spherical in shape. The spectra given by the LE₂, PE₂ and RE₂ combinations of two prominent absorption bands – a low wavelength transverse absorption band in the visible region (out-of-plane vibration band) and a longer wavelength longitudinal absorption band in the NIR region (in-plane plasmon vibrations) – indicated that the synthesized nanoparticles possessed an intrinsic anisotropy^{20–22}. This was also confirmed from the SEM and TEM studies.

Table 1 presents the extract-metal concentration ratios that gave maximum GNP yield – as reflected in the highest SPR peaks achieved for that plant-part. Table 2 illus-

trates the pattern of GNP formation as a function of time. The optical density of the nanoparticles was found to increase gradually with increase in reaction duration, attaining a maximum and then beginning to decline.

The GNP formation was found to be more than 90% within 2 h for the petiole extract (PE₁), while the rate of GNP formation was slower with other plant parts.

The nanoparticles arising from different plant parts and reactant proportions were characterized for their size, shape, purity and crystal structure by employing SEM, Hr-SEM, TEM, EDX, XRD and SAED techniques. The biomolecules that could possibly be responsible for the reduction of the metal ions to nanoparticles and the subsequent stabilization and capping of the nanoparticles were identified using FT-IR spectroscopy.

Electron microscopic (SEM, Hr-SEM, TEM) and EDX studies :

The morphology and size of the synthesized gold nanoparticles were determined using SEM, Hr-SEM, TEM and SAED analysis. The elemental composition of the nanoparticles was confirmed by EDX analysis.

The SEM and Hr-SEM micrographs recorded for the nanoparticles synthesized from the LE₁, PE₁ and RE₁ combinations (Figs. 3a, 3c and 3e) show that the

Fig. 1a. UV-Visible spectra of LE₁ gold nanoparticles synthesis; Inset : plot of the intensity of the surface plasmon resonances of LE₁ against the reaction duration.

Fig. 1b. UV-Visible spectra of LE_2 gold nanoparticles synthesis; Inset : plot of the intensity of the surface plasmon resonances of LE_2 against the reaction duration.

Fig. 2a. UV-Visible spectra of PE_1 gold nanoparticles synthesis; Inset : plot of the intensity of the surface plasmon resonances of PE_1 against the reaction duration.

nanoparticles are spherical in shape. The TEM micrographs for the same mixtures shows that the size of the nanoparticles ranges from 4–18 nm, 12–30 nm and 3–20 nm respectively for the LE_1 , PE_1 and RE_1 combinations (Figs. 4a, 4c and 4e).

The SEM, Hr-SEM and TEM images revealing the shapes and sizes of the nanoparticles formed from the LE_2 , PE_2 and RE_2 combinations are presented in Figs. 3b, 3d, 3f, 4b, 4d and 4f. It is seen that these reaction combinations resulted in anisotropic nanoparticles of tri-

Fig. 2b. UV-Visible spectra of PE₂ gold nanoparticles synthesis; Inset : plot of the intensity of the surface plasmon resonances of PE₂ against the reaction duration.

Fig. 2c. UV-Visible spectra of RE₁ gold nanoparticles synthesis; Inset : plot of the intensity of the surface plasmon resonances of RE₁ against the reaction duration.

angular, hexagonal, pentagonal, and truncated triangular shapes. The sizes of the nanoparticles ranged from 80–94 nm, 81–96 nm and 57–94 nm respectively for the reaction combinations LE₂, PE₂ and RE₂.

The spot-profile EDX spectrum shows a strong signal

for gold atoms in the nanoparticles (Insets of Figs. 3a and 3f). Weak signals from carbon, nitrogen and oxygen atoms are also seen which are likely to be due to X-ray emission from proteins/enzymes present in the residual plant extracts present along with the nanoparticles. An

Fig. 2d. UV-Visible spectra of RE₂ gold nanoparticles synthesis; Inset : plot of the intensity of the surface plasmon resonances of RE₂ against the reaction duration.

optical absorption band at approximately 2 keV is seen, which is characteristic of gold nanoparticles^{7,8}.

Table 1. Extract-metal combinations yielding maximum GNPs of type I (represented by symbol E₁) and type II (represented by symbol E₂) spectra for different parts of *E. crassipes*

Plant part used for preparing the extract	Concentration relative to Au ^{III}	
	Extract	Au ^{III}
Leaf (LE ₁)	3000	50
Leaf (LE ₂)	7000	100
Petiole (PE ₁)	1000	170
Petiole (PE ₂)	5000	170
Root (RE ₁)	1000	100
Root (RE ₂)	7500	85

The SAED patterns are shown in Figs. 4a and 4f. The bright circular spots complement the Bragg's planes representing crystalline nature of the gold nanoparticles, as reported by Philip²³. The electron micrographs reveal that the nanoparticles were stable and there was no aggregation of particles in the solution after centrifugation (Figs. 4a and 4f).

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) studies :

The powder XRD analysis was used to determine the crystalline structure of the synthesized nanoparticles. The diffractograms (Fig. 5b) have intense peaks at the 2θ position, matching with (111), (200), (220) and (311) Bragg's

Table 2. Pattern of GNP formation as a function of time

Extract + Metal ion mixture	0th h		2nd h		4th h		6th h		24th h	
	λ _{max}	Abs.								
LE ₁	531	0.075	538	0.861	531	0.920	531	0.927	537	1.000
LE ₂	-	-	540	1.832	535	1.967	536	2.035	534	1.699
			1022	1.235	992	1.312	991	1.429	996	1.324
PE ₁	527	0.257	530	0.401	529	0.394	530	0.387	531	0.393
PE ₂	538	1.706	797	0.714	535	1.754	535	1.817	536	1.562
					811	0.780	822	0.870	863	0.739
RE ₁	-	-	533	0.542	531	0.569	531	0.573	541	0.789
RE ₂	-	-	557	1.522	533	1.756	550	1.958	544	1.821
			933	0.917	866	1.117	807	1.270	776	1.105

Fig. 3a. A composite visual of (i) scanning electron micrograph; (ii) and (iii) high resolution scanning electron micrographs (Inset is the EDX spectrum) of LE_1 gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 3b. A composite visual of (a) scanning electron micrograph; (b) and (c) high resolution scanning electron micrographs (Inset is the EDX spectrum) of LE_2 gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 3c. A composite visual of (i) scanning electron micrograph; (ii) and (iii) high resolution scanning electron micrographs (Inset is the EDX spectrum) of PE_1 gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 3d. A composite visual of (a) scanning electron micrograph; (b) and (c) high resolution scanning electron micrographs (Inset is the EDX spectrum) of PE_2 gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 3e. A composite visual of (i) scanning electron micrograph; (ii) and (iii) high resolution scanning electron micrographs (Inset is the EDX spectrum) of RE_1 gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 3f. A composite visual of (a) scanning electron micrograph; (b) and (c) high resolution scanning electron micrographs (Inset is the EDX spectrum) of RE_2 gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 4a. A composite visual of transmission electron micrographs (i-v) showing spherical particles of LE_1 at different magnifications and (vi) SAED pattern of the gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 4b. A composite visual of transmission electron micrographs (a–e) showing spherical and anisotropic particles of LE_2 at different magnifications and (f) SAED pattern of the gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 4c. A composite visual of transmission electron micrographs (i–v) showing spherical particles of PE_1 at different magnifications and (vi) SAED pattern of the gold nanoparticles.

planes and indicating a face centered cubic structure of the nanoparticles⁵ (Table 3). The XRD patterns which match with the database of JCPDS file no. 04-0784, con-

firm that the synthesized gold nanoparticles are of pure crystalline nature. The crystalline domain size of the nanoparticles were calculated using the Debye-Scherrer's

Fig. 4d. A composite visual of transmission electron micrographs (a–e) showing spherical and anisotropic particles of PE₂ at different magnifications and (f) SAED pattern of the gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 4e. A composite visual of transmission electron micrographs (i–v) showing spherical particles of RE₁ at different magnifications and (vi) SAED pattern of the gold nanoparticles.

equation by obtaining the FWHM of the (111) Bragg's reflection from the XRD spectrum²⁴.

Average crystallite sizes of the gold nanoparticles were found to be from 14.6 to 29.9 nm. The particle sizes as

seen from XRD (Fig. 5a) are in agreement with the average size *ca.* 14.5 nm obtained from the electron micrographs. This reveals the formation of monodispersed spherical particles. The particle size calculated from XRD

Fig. 4f. A composite visual of transmission electron micrographs (a–e) showing spherical and anisotropic particles of RE_2 at different magnifications and (f) SAED pattern of the gold nanoparticles.

Table 3. 2θ position of the Bragg's plane observed from the X-ray diffractograms

Bragg's plane	(111)	(200)	(220)	(311)
2θ position				
LE ₁	38.19	44.25	64.17	77.31
LE ₂	38.11	44.31	64.43	77.85
PE ₁	38.85	44.41	65.19	78.05
PE ₂	38.07	44.69	64.13	76.73
RE ₁	38.85	45.01	65.35	78.07
RE ₂	38.79	44.91	65.25	78.19

pattern (Fig. 5a) is less than that of the size determined from the electron micrographs. This is probably because the synthesized gold nanoparticles are of polycrystalline nature²⁵. The ratio of optical densities between the (200) and (111) Bragg's diffraction peaks are in the range of 0.25–0.44. This is found to be lesser than the intensity ratio (i.e. 0.52) of conventional bulk gold, indicating the presence of nanoparticles with (111) facets²⁶.

Fourier transform infra-red (FT-IR) spectroscopy :

FT-IR analysis was used to identify the functional group of the biomolecules found in the plant extract which could have been involved in the bioreduction and capping/stabilization of the synthesized nanoparticles. The FT-IR spectra (Fig. 5b) was able to show that proteins and polyols of terpenoids, flavones and polysaccharides were possibly

involved in the bioreduction and capping/stabilization of the synthesized nanoparticles.

The FT-IR pattern of leaf extract showed the presence of medium or strong absorption bands at 1628 cm^{-1} , 1609 cm^{-1} , 1119 cm^{-1} . The strongest of the bands can be assigned to amide I^{27,28}. The peak was found to shift to 1663 cm^{-1} and 1598 cm^{-1} in the gold nanoparticles. Additionally peak at 1030 cm^{-1} corresponding to the polyols in the polysaccharides exhibited by the leaf extract was found to disappear in the gold nanoparticle. This shows that proteins and polysaccharides found in the leaf extract could be responsible for the reduction of the gold ions and also acts as an efficient capping agent ensuring the stability of the nanoparticles.

The peaks in the spectra of nanoparticles obtained with the petiole extracts were found at 1650 cm^{-1} , 1453 cm^{-1} , and 1072 cm^{-1} . In this case, too, strongest band can be attributed to amide I^{27,28}. Bands corresponding to amide I and triterpenoids at 1072 cm^{-1} ²⁹ were found to be shifted in the gold nanoparticles. The peak at 1602 cm^{-1} corresponding to nucleic acid was found to disappear in the gold nanoparticles. This indicates that proteins, nucleic acid and terpenoids found in the petiole extract could have interacted in the bioreduction and capping/stabilization of synthesized gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 5a. X-Ray diffraction spectrum of (i) LE₁, (ii) LE₂, (iii) PE₁, (iv) PE₂, (v) RE₁ and (vi) RE₂ gold nanoparticles.

The recorded spectral patterns of the root extract was found with the bands at 1666.5 cm⁻¹, 1609 cm⁻¹, 1320 cm⁻¹, 1185 cm⁻¹, 1106 cm⁻¹ corresponding to amide I, polyol, C–O stretching, ester and polyols of terpenoids, flavones and polysaccharides respectively²⁷⁻²⁹. On comparing the spectra of root extract and gold nanoparticles, Fig. 5b reveals the presence of minor changes in the posi-

tions as well as on the magnitude of the absorption bands. With closer examination, the spectrum of gold nanoparticles shows a minor shift to 1649 cm⁻¹ and disappearance of band at 1106 cm⁻¹. Hence, it can be inferred that proteins and polyols of terpenoids, flavones and polysaccharides could have played a role in the bioreduction and capping/stabilization of the gold nanoparticles.

References

1. S. A. Abbasi, T. Abbasi and J. Anuradha, *Offl. J. Patent Off.*, 2012b, 20.04, 61.
2. S. A. Abbasi, T. Abbasi, J. Anuradha, N. Neghi, S. Pirathiba and S. U. Ganaie, *Offl. J. Patent Off.*, 2011, 11869.
3. J. Anuradha, T. Abbasi and S. A. Abbasi, *Res. J. Biotech.*, 2010, **5**, 75.
4. J. Anuradha, T. Abbasi and S. A. Abbasi, *Res. J. Biotech.*, 2011a, **6**, 69.
5. J. Anuradha, T. Abbasi and S. A. Abbasi, *Inter. J. Environ. Sci. & Eng. Res.*, 2011b, **2**, 1.
6. J. Anuradha, T. Abbasi and S. A. Abbasi, "Facile 'phyto' fabrication of silver nanoparticles of diverse geometries with concomitant utilization of a pernicious terrestrial weed", in : 'Proceedings of the International Conference on Green Technology and Environmental Conservation (GTEC-2011)', Sathyabama University, Chennai, IEEE, 2011c, 216-223.
7. APHA (American Public Health Association), Standard methods of water and wastewater, 22nd ed., American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association and Water Environment Federation publication, Washington D.C., USA, 2012.
8. H. Borchert, E. V. Shevchenko, A. Robert, I. Mekis, A. Kornowski and G. Grubel, *Langmuir.*, 2005, **21**, 1931.
9. S. C. G. K. Daniel, K. Nehru and M. Sivakumar, *Current Nanoscience*, 2012a, **8**, 125.
10. R. C. Elgersma, D. T. S. Rijkers and R. M. J. Liskamp, *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.*, 2009, **61**, 239.
11. P. Ghosh, G. Han, M. De, C. K. Kim and V. M. Rotello, *Adv. Drug Deliver. Rev.*, 2008, **60**, 1307.
12. P. G. Kareru, J. M. Keriko, A. N. Gachanja and G. M. Kenji, *African J. Trad. Compl. Alternative Med.*, 2008, **5**, 56.
13. V. Khare, Z. Li, A. Manton, A. A. Ayi, S. Sonkaria, A. Voelkl and A. F. Thunemann, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2010, **20**, 1332.
14. C. Kumar, "Biomimetic and bioinspired nanomaterials", Wiley-VCH, USA, 2010.
15. S. Link and M. A. El-Sayed, *Annu. Re. Phys. Chem.*, 2003, **54**, 331.
16. S. Liu, D. Leech and H. Ju, *Anal. Lett.*, 2003, **36**, 1.
17. L. M. Liz-Marzan, *Langmuir*, 2006, **22**, 32.
18. T. Mochochoko, O. S. Oluwafemi, D. N. Jumbam, S. P. Songca and T. Mochochoko, *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 2013, **98**, 290.
19. P. Mulvaney, *Langmuir*, 1996, **12**, 788.
20. S. Navaladian, B. Viswanathan, T. K. Varadarajan and R. P. Viswanath, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.*, 2008, **4**, 181.
21. D. T. Nguyen, D. J. Kim, M. G. So and K. S. Kim, *Adv. Powder Technol.*, 2010, **21**, 111.
22. D. Philip, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A*, 2009, **73**, 374.
23. S. Pirathiba, M.Tech. Thesis, Pondicherry University, India, 2011.
24. D. Raghunandan, M. D. Bedre, S. Basavaraja, B. Sawle, S. Y. Manjunath and A. Venkataraman, *Colloid. Surface (B)*, 2010, **79**, 235.
25. S. S. Shankar, A. Ahmad, R. Parsricha and M. Sastry, *J. Mat. Chem.*, 2003, **13**, 1822.
26. S. S. Shankar, A. Rai, A. Ahmad and M. Sastry, *Chem. Mater.*, 2005, **17**, 566.
27. P. Tiwari, K. Vig, V. Dennis and S. Singh, *Nanomaterials*, 2011, **1**, 31.
28. M. Valdes, A. Valdes Gonzalez, J. Garcia Calzon and M. Diaz-garcia, *Microchim. Acta*, 2009, **166**, 1.
29. B. Wen, J. Ma, C. Chen, W. Ma, H. Zhu and J. Zhao, *Sci. China Chem.*, 2011, **54**, 887.

